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Living in Hope: *Fratelli Tutti*, Friendship and Forgiveness for a Sustainable Humanity

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Abstract: Basing ourselves on Pope Francis' *Tratelli Tutti* and the life of Charles de Foucauld, in this article, we make an attempt to outline a life lived in hope. After exploring the prophetic image of Charles de Foucauld we look at the worth of everyone who is abandoned. Then we try to converse with the others in a friendly manner leading to the overcoming of suspicion and conflict. This helps us to live our lives based on the two principles of forgiveness and friendship, which

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alone will enable us to live in hope and foster a sustainable world community. So we are challenged to walk on the path of living and sustaining hope! Hope for a just, egalitarian and love-filled world! A world of care, concern and compassion, especially for the weak and vulnerable!

Keywords: Fratelli Tutti, Hope, Best of Politics, Best of Religion, Charles de Foucauld, Friendship and Forgiveness

Introduction

How can we find traces of hope in the world we live in? How is Pope Francis' *Fratelli Tutti* an encyclical of realistic hope? How can we go forward with hope and joy and make ourselves and the world better? These are some of the questions we post in this article, that reflects on hope in *Fratelli Tutti*.

a. A Meditation on Living Hope

In this encyclical, Pope Francis invites everyone to renewed hope, for hope “speaks to us of something deeply rooted in every human heart, independently of our circumstances and historical conditioning. Hope speaks to us of a thirst, an aspiration, a longing for a life of fulfilment, a desire to achieve great things, things that fill our heart and lift our spirit to lofty realities like truth, goodness and beauty, justice and love... Hope is bold; it can look beyond personal convenience, the petty securities and compensations which limit our horizon, and it can open us up to grand ideals that make life more beautiful and worthwhile.” Let us continue, then, to advance along the paths of hope” (FT 55).

The noteworthy affirmation here is, “Hope is bold.” What does that mean in the context of this document and our pandemic era? Hope is far less than a straightforward future expectation. It alludes to something that can be felt after a long and harrowing journey. It could be a set period. It could be a trial that places demands on the individual. However, it is not a pipe dream or a fantasy. It suggests that something “More beautiful and worthwhile” can be a part of God’s plan for us. We are not

condemned to a future bleak and in decline from what our older generations have lived and experienced (Modern 2020).

b. Frustrated by injustice?

In this encyclical, Pope Francis challenges us to seek solutions to the injustices and growing indifference occurring throughout the world (Olea, 2020). It is mainly addressed to those who are frustrated by the injustice they perceive all around them.

An activist holds that “this is the type of reading that brings me a fresh wave of hope. This work, positioned next to the divisiveness and political trauma we’ve endured, offers the world renewed sense of hope” (Olea, 2020). She adds further that those who have felt frustrated with the injustices they have experienced may receive Christ’s living hope through this encyclical.

What touched the activist was Pope Francis’ centering this encyclical on the parable of the good Samaritan. The title of this second chapter, ‘A stranger on the road’ makes those who have experienced injustice feel it deeply. The activist ruminates: “I, too, am a stranger. For my entire life, I have been neither from here nor there. I have spent years adapting, relearning, moulding, trying to fit in as the perfect immigrant” (Olea, 2020).

In this hope-filled encyclical, Pope Francis “affirmed my dignity as a daughter of Christ. No, it is not my fault that my life has been used as a political pawn, a part of the throwaway culture we have created. This is not God’s will” (Olea, 2020).

While Pope Francis, of course, did not change the prevalent injustice, he addresses, recognizes and hears it. Pope Francis

noted that so much injustice has been disguised as justice, which only deepens the wound of the inflicted.

This resonates with the social activist who cares for the poor and the migrant. Drawing hope from the letter, he affirms: “Yet, we will continue to advocate for immigrant rights because it truly works of justice. It’s holy work” (Olea, 2020).

The motivation for the work for the poor and the vulnerable have “come from my belief in dignity and justice for all — not some — not the rich — not just for privileged — for all.” She is convinced that “fighting against policies designed to further alienate poor and vulnerable immigrants is the work of Christ. What an honour to be able to do this work” (Olea, 2020).

Further, she holds that “Pope Francis’ willingness to write about our dark reality, which is uncomfortable and challenging, is why I was given a renewed sense of hope. We cannot bring light to darkness if we don’t allow ourselves to see darkness.”

Brothers and sisters, we cannot only pray for better days. We have to be willing to be the reason better days will come. Do we recognize our own role as the good Samaritan? (Olea, 2020).

It provided us with hope when the pope affirms, “Sincere and humble worship of God ‘bears fruit not in discrimination, hatred and violence, but in respect for the sacredness of life, respect for the dignity and freedom of others, and loving commitment to the welfare of all’” (No. 283). Pope Francis’ reflection in this encyclical and particularly on the Good Samaritan offers a poignant examination of our interior selves. (Briscoe, 2020). It offers rays of hope to those who are terribly frustrated by experiences of injustice around them.

c. The Outline

So in this article, basing ourselves on Pope Francis’ *Tratelli Tutti* and the life of Charles de Foucauld, we make an attempt to outline a life lived in hope. After exploring the prophetic image of Charles de Foucauld we look at the worth of everyone who is

abandoned. Then we try to converse with the others in a friendly manner leading to the overcoming of suspicion and conflict. This helps us to live our lives based on the two principles of forgiveness and friendship, which alone will enable us to live in hope and foster a sustainable world community.

1. Living in Hope: Charles de Foucauld in *Fratelli Tutti*

This new encyclical on fraternity and social friendship, inspired by St. Francis of Assisi, the saint of fraternal love for all creatures, especially our abandoned brothers and sisters, focuses on the proclamation of Christianity's essential obligations: adoration of God and service to our neighbours. It states: “We believers are challenged to return to our sources, to concentrate on what is essential: worship of God and love for our neighbour, so that some of our teachings, taken out of context, do not end up feeding forms of contempt, hatred, xenophobia or negation of others” (FT 282).

Pope Francis is not bothered by his critics, those who claim his speeches are too concerned with politics and say little about eschatology (Fares, 2020).¹ Rather, following the criteria that the Lord has given us in the parable of the Good Samaritan, he removes eschatology from the sphere of abstract affirmations about the end of time and places it in our present-day reality, on the “roadside,” where we “come to know ourselves through our relationships with our

¹ For this section I am indebted to the enlightening article by Diago Fares (2020) which was originally published *La Civiltà Cattolica*, a periodical published by the Jesuits in Rome, Italy, since 1850. For the original article please see <https://www.laciviltacattolica.it/articolo/la-figura-di-charles-de-foucauld-in-fratelli-tutti/>.

brothers and sisters,” whenever “we encounter a person who is suffering” (FT 69).

If there were any doubts about what Francis wishes to announce and witness during his pontificate, he returns in this new encyclical to point out where social issues, the economy, politics, and religious life play out, undivided and unconfused: “Today there are more and more injured people. The decision to include or exclude those lying wounded along the roadside can serve as a criterion for judging every economic, political, social and religious project” (FT 69).

2. The Prophetic Image of Charles de Foucauld: Dreaming Together

Along with the opening image of Francis of Assisi, a closing image of Charles de Foucauld encircles the entire content of the encyclical in a hopeful embrace. The pope dynamically summarizes the encyclical by emphasizing fraternity and social friendship: “It is my desire that, in this our time, by acknowledging the dignity of each human person, we can contribute to the rebirth of a universal aspiration to fraternity” (FT 8). Let us dream together, he exhorts us at the beginning. And he repeats the suggestion at the end: “May God inspire in each of us the dream that inspired Charles de Foucauld” (cf. FT 287, Fares, 2020).

The figure of the soon-to-be-canonised Charles de Foucauld² serves as a great testimonial force in *Fratelli Tutti*: He gathers and updates Francis of Assisi's legacy, synthesizes and embodies Gospel content, and challenges us concretely wherever the most pressing issues of our time arise.

The pope's final two paragraphs, which he explicitly dedicates to Blessed Charles de Foucauld, are brief but dense with evangelical

² It may be noted that Blessed Charles de Foucauld will be canonised on May 15, 2022 along with the Indian Blessed Lazarus or Devasagayam. See (Vatican News. 2021).

content. Francis describes de Foucauld's dream of total self-giving to God and his brothers and sisters, allowing him to become "brother of all" or "universal brother." de Foucauld understood that he could realise this only by "identifying himself with the least" (FT 287; cf. 2-4). The most important thing the pope points out to us is that this is not a random dream. It comes weighted with history: the dream of Blessed Charles is the same one that God inspired in Francis of Assisi. It is an ideal long dreamed, an ideal that also involves a path of transformation within us, to make us feel ourselves to be brothers, sisters and friends of all, just like these saints (Pandikattu 2005).

This dream of fraternity and social friendship has always been among the primary concerns of Pope Francis (cf. FT 5). And we note that de Foucauld's spirituality does not appear only in the final paragraphs but pervades the entire encyclical. In addition to the explicit reference to fraternity and social friendship specific to this saint, Farres highlight aspects of his spirituality that are extensively present in *Fratelli Tutti*.

3. The Worth of the Abandoned

In chapter three, the "stranger on the roadside" is called "the abandoned," an expression that the pope uses to speak of the concreteness of Francis of Assisi's universal love and Charles de Foucauld's identification "with the poor, abandoned deep in the African desert" (FT 287).

This preference for the most abandoned has an ethical as well as a deeply theological underpinning. In Charles de Foucauld's life, abandonment into the hands of the Father ("prayer of abandonment") and embracing the least in their abandonment are synonymous: "Embrace humility, poverty, abandonment, abjection, loneliness, suffering with Jesus in the manger; do not make any case for human greatness,

elevation, the esteem of men, but esteem the poor as well as the rich. As for me, I always aim to seek the last of the last places, to order my life so as to be the last, the most despised of men” (Cited in Fares, 2020).

It is worth noting that de Foucauld not only searches for the abandoned one by one, but he also captures all of the people in each of them: to be more specific, he searches for the most abandoned peoples. According to Blessed Charles: “Since no people seemed to be more abandoned than these, I urged my request and obtained permission from the Apostolic Prefect of the Sahara to settle in the Algerian Sahara and to lead you into solitude, seclusion and silence, manual labour and holy poverty, alone or with some priest or lay brother in Jesus, a life as far as possible in accordance with the life of the beloved Jesus in Nazareth” (Fares, 2020).

What is the value of a human being? In this encyclical, Francis tells us that a human being has a value not only because he is worthy of justice and mercy, because he is a brother or sister, and because he is equal in humanity, but also because he is worthy of being our friend. “As the Latin American Bishops taught, ‘only the closeness that makes us friends can enable us to appreciate deeply the values of the poor today, their legitimate desires, and their own manner of living the faith. The option for the poor should lead us to friendship with the poor’” (FT 234, Fares, 2020)

4. The Conversation with Friends

Chapter six, on dialogue and social friendship, reflects the wisdom of Charles de Foucauld’s own resolution to “increase my conversation with the humble, shorten it with the powerful.” Worthy of note is the emphasis on dialogue in his way of approaching his Muslim brothers: “Approaching them, making contact, befriending them, making their prejudices against us fall, through daily and friendly relations; changing, through

conversation and the example of our life, their ideas” (Cited in Fares, 2020).

His conversation stems from more than just his natural sociability, nor is it merely a pastoral strategy. Prayer, for him, is the most important thing in life because it allows him to communicate with God: “Prayer is any conversation of the soul with God [...], an intimate conversation, a delightful secret” (Cited in Fares, 2020). And it is precisely this most precious dimension of his that he offers to the most humble people he meets. Charles de Foucauld is one of those men of whom one can say, as the highest praise, “he speaks to everyone,” a person who makes no distinction between people, not only as regards being just and open, but also as regards the kind of conversation that we reserve only for those we consider worthy of friendship.

In the first chapter entitled, “The shadows of a closed world,” the pope goes beyond a criticism of the degradation affecting dialogue through false news, slander and denigration of neighbours, which are so damaging to the political and social life of a country and the world. Francis goes to the heart of a friendly dialogue because it is the only one capable of uniting humanity, of making us speak in the first person plural, saying “us” with the heart. He says: “They lack the physical gestures, facial expressions, moments of silence, body language and even the smells, the trembling of hands, the blushes and perspiration that speak to us and are a part of human communication. Digital relationships, which do not demand the slow and gradual cultivation of friendships, stable interaction or the building of a consensus that matures over time, have the appearance of sociability. Yet they do not really build community; instead, they tend to disguise and expand the very individualism that finds expression in xenophobia and in contempt for the vulnerable. Digital

connectivity is not enough to build bridges. It is not capable of uniting humanity” (FT 43).

There is a way of conversing that is only possible with social friendship. The pope's goal is to build consensus around the fundamental truth of every human being's absolute dignity, the pleasure of recognizing the other, and the recovery of kindness. When speaking with friends, these are the modes of communication that are fully in place. (Fares, 2020)

Such conversion or dialogue means going deeper than “feverish exchange” (FT 200) on social media and a “noisy potpourri of facts and opinions” (FT 201) we often find in the traditional media. Political leaders practising dialogue would recognize that others have something valuable to contribute and that conflicting points of view are worthy of respect.

The true encounter does not push others away because they make us uncomfortable; it is rooted in a “basic sense of belonging” to each other which is present within each human being (230). It does not mean avoiding conflicts or “making society blandly uniform” (FT 228). Political leaders practising encounters would foster reconciliation that happens through “open, honest, and patient negotiation” (FT 244, Jones, 2020)

Leaders who show solidarity would practice “thinking and acting in terms of community,” and would recognize that being born in one place or another does not make a person more or less worthy of the rights and privileges of being human (FT 116). On the contrary, “the dignity of others is to be respected in all circumstances, not because that dignity is something we have invented or imagined, but because human beings possess an intrinsic worth” that comes from God (FT 213).

This call for dialogue, encounter, and solidarity politics may appear utopian or naive. Francis admits this several times. Yet, he reminds us that change happens on the level of ordinary people, and that “each individual can act as an effective leaven by the way he or she lives each day” (FT 231). In a very practical way, we

can strive to change our lives day by day according to the model of the Good Samaritan, and we can vote for the political leaders who best exemplify this “better kind of politics.” No candidate, or society, will ever be perfect, but we must not lose hope: Francis reminds us that “God continues to sow abundant seeds of goodness in our human family” (FT 54, Jones, 2020)

5. The Overcoming of Conflicts through the Intimate and the Universal

The figure of Charles de Foucauld assumes a paradigmatic stature in the perspective of Francis, who presents him as the one who embodied in our time the Gospel truth of the yeast that ferments the dough.³

The pope returns to this intimate concern in the encyclical in a broader context of reflection (cf. FT 5), where he seeks to universalize what exists most freely and intimately, such as friendship, so that fraternity can take root deeply in humanity's social and political life. In fact, fraternity is insufficient. From Cain on, the conflicts between brothers – from inheritance disputes to civil wars – are frequently the most ferocious. It is necessary to cultivate freely offered friendship in order to have a good fraternal relationship. This adds the qualitative component of the free choice to be friends to fraternity and thus consolidates a fraternal relationship that, because it is based on an unchosen common

³ According to the German theologian, Romano *Guardini* (1885 – 1968), whom the Pope cherishes, only what is more intimate can be transformed into something truly universal; and only what is more universal can be radically internalised. This contrasts with all false universalism and all false intimacy.

origin, can lead to friendship as much as the opposite (Fares, 2020).

The pope's discernment of social exclusion as the evil of our time leads us to the conclusion that it can only be resolved by an intimate and gratuitous reality such as the desire for friendship, which involves considering the other not only as equal in dignity, despite differences of race, religion, or social condition, but also as capable of friendship. The figure of Charles de Foucauld, far removed from that of the solitary little friar dedicated to a heroic but individual and inimitable mission, before our eyes are transformed into a universal figure, who carries out a mission that is totally imitable and programmatic. It was his intuition, for example, that in order to prepare the Muslim world for the coming of the Gospel and Christ, slow work of establishing unconditional friendship and service is required, without the pretension of imposing any universal truth. He universalised the Christian service practised toward every person he met, and not simply general Christian ideas. On these, rather, he was silent. He declared: "Such is the pastor, such is the people." "The good that a soul does is in direct proportion to its inner spirit." "The sanctification of the peoples of this region is, therefore, in my hands! They will be saved if I become holy."¹

Let us examine how intense the relationship between the radicality of Blessed de Foucauld's personal holiness and the force of universal irradiation of that same holiness to all peoples is in Blessed de Foucauld. This is exemplified by the parable of the yeast in the dough. But Pope Francis also demonstrates the other side of the coin: the relationship between interiority and universality is not a one-way street in which the more interior one becomes, the more universal one becomes. Francis teaches us that there is no true universality that does not attempt to take root in the most fundamental values, which are both free and gratuitous. A politics that does not cultivate a desire for friendship among the people and instead focuses on manipulating attitudes and votes from without will never be true politics, that is, service to the

common good. And, although it appears to take longer, we can say the same about the economy: an economic system that does not reach out to the most marginalized will eventually collapse on a global scale (Fares, 2020).

And, going a step further, we can say the same thing about joy and beauty: a joy that not everyone can rejoice in, that only a few can share selfishly, is not a complete joy. It's missing something. Everything is interconnected, and the relationship between interiority and universality is about being, not theory (Pandikattu, 2019).

6. The Principles of Forgiveness and Friendship

This healthy and fundamental connection between interiority and universality also illuminates those famous principles the pope always recalls: the principle that the whole is more than the part, and even more than the mere sum of the parts (cf. FT 78; 145; 215); and the principle that “unity is superior to conflict” (FT 245). These should not be read in the line of abstract reasoning, opposing the different definitions of each concept, but in the vital sense that goes beyond any definition, because it is expressed in the asymmetrical tension that is given between what exists in the most intimate and gratuitous setting, and what can be expected to be more universal (Fares, 2020).

The pope asserts that universality is rooted in the intimacy of what is more local: “There is a false openness to the universal, which derives from the empty superficiality of those who are not able to penetrate deeply into their own homeland, or of those who carry an unresolved resentment toward their own people. In any case, ‘we constantly have to broaden our horizons and see the greater good which will benefit us all. But this has to be done without evasion or uprooting. We need to sink our roots deeper into the fertile soil and history of our native place, which is a gift of God.

We can work on a small scale, in our own neighbourhood, but with a larger perspective...The global need not stifle, nor the particular prove barren.’ Our model must be that of a polyhedron, in which the value of each individual is respected, where ‘the whole is greater than the part, but it is also greater than the sum of its parts’ (FT 145).

The image of the Good Samaritan sums up this relationship between dealing with the whole heart of a single case and building of an “us” around it. For this, “we can start from below and, case by case, act at the most concrete and local levels, and then expand to the farthest reaches of our countries and our world, with the same care and concern that the Samaritan showed for each of the wounded man’s injuries. [...] Yet let us not do this alone, as individuals. The Samaritan discovered an innkeeper who would care for the man; we too are called to unite as a family that is stronger than the sum of small individual members. For ‘the whole is greater than the part, but it is also greater than the sum of its parts’” (FT 78).

In the same way, the union capable of overcoming conflicts is the one that is rooted “in the highest dimension of ourselves.” “On numerous occasions, I have spoken of ‘a principle indispensable to the building of friendship in society, namely, that unity is greater than conflict... This is not to opt for a kind of syncretism, or for the absorption of one into the other, but rather for a resolution which takes place on a higher plane and preserves what is valid and useful on both sides.’ All of us know that ‘when we, as individuals and communities, learn to look *beyond* ourselves and our particular interests, then understanding and mutual commitment bear fruit... in a setting where conflicts, tensions and even groups once considered hostile can attain a multifaceted unity that gives rise to new life’” (FT 245, Fares, 2020).

Speaking of his desire to be a universal brother, Charles de Foucauld opines: “The natives seem to welcome us well. This reception is not sincere; they give in to necessity... How long will it take for them to have the feelings they simulate? It may be that

they will never have them. If they do, it will be the day when they will be Christians... Will they know how to distinguish between soldiers and priests; to see in us servants of God, ministers of peace and charity, universal brothers? I don't know... If I fulfil my duty, Jesus will spread abundant graces, and they will understand" (Cited in Fares, 2020).

Francis, in this context, points out two things as the highest and most intimate, because they are fully free: forgiveness and friendship. (Fares, 2020)

a. Forgiveness

After a detailed phenomenological description in which he admits all the difficulties and deviations connected with the idea of forgiveness, the pope speaks to us of "free and heartfelt forgiveness," which is "a reflection of God's own infinite ability to forgive." He writes: "If forgiveness is gratuitous, then it can be shown even to someone who resists repentance and is unable to beg pardon" (FT 250). In one of the most original passages of the encyclical, the pope states that forgiveness does not mean forgetting, and specifies his proposal: "In the face of a reality that can in no way be denied, relativised or concealed, forgiveness *is still possible*. In the face of an action that can never be tolerated, justified or excused, *we can still* forgive. In the face of something that cannot be forgotten for any reason, *we can still* forgive" (FT 250; italics ours). We see here, expressed as what is most universally able to be demanded, the condition without which a fraternal society cannot be built: forgiveness. That is, we see that it can only be given as a free and gratuitous interior act.

The pope does not say "we must" but "we can" forgive. This decision – choosing to forgive – is not idealistic or a purely religious matter. Any alliance – local, national or worldwide – always implies a decision to forgive certain things in order

to move forward. Forgiveness as a free decision is at the root of any policy that seeks the common good.

b. Friendship

Further, Francis points out: “Social friendship and universal fraternity necessarily call for an acknowledgement of the worth of every human person, always and everywhere. If each individual is of such great worth, it must be stated clearly and firmly that ‘the mere fact that some people are born in places with fewer resources or less development does not justify the fact that they are living with less dignity.’ This is a basic principle of social life that tends to be ignored in a variety of ways by those who sense that it does not fit into their worldview or serve their purposes” (FT 106).

Reflecting on friendship, Francis emphasises what he calls the “law of ecstasy,” of going out of oneself to find in the other potential for the growth of our being (Fares, 2020). “In the depths of every heart, love creates bonds and expands existence, for it draws people out of themselves and toward others. Since we were made for love, in each one of us a law of *ekstasis* seems to operate: ‘the lover *goes outside* the self to find a fuller existence in another.’ For this reason, ‘people must take up the challenge of moving beyond themselves” (FT 88).

This is why the noblest forms of friendship are found in the hearts that let themselves be completed. The bonds binding couples and friends open the heart around us, making us capable of going out of ourselves to welcome everyone (cf. FT 89). The most proper characteristic of friendship is love for others as such, and this moves us to seek the best for them. “Only by cultivating this way of relating to one another will we make possible a social friendship that excludes no one and a fraternity that is open to all” (FT 94).

7. Choosing the Best of Politics and of Religions

Thus we see how the tension between interiority and universality is the one that builds the best politics and fosters dialogue between the best aspects of each religion.

The pope's message on politics, however, speaks to this current climate in a particularly striking way. Pope Francis admits that “for many people today, politics is a distasteful word” (FT 176). Corruption, poor governance, and seemingly hopeless division have led to a high degree of cynicism toward political leaders in many countries. On the contrary, he considers politics a noble profession, but only if leaders practice it “out of a tender care for others” (FT 194). Politicians have a unique opportunity: they can help individuals, yes, but they also have the power to create the very conditions by which people can flourish, which has a much larger impact. Politics has fallen into disrepute because individualism and an unhealthy populism have corrupted it. What we need, says Francis, is “a better kind of politics, one truly at the service of the common good” (FT 154, Jones, 2020).

The pope adds: “Recognising that all people are our brothers and sisters, and seeking forms of social friendship that include everyone, is not merely utopian. It demands a decisive commitment to devising effective means to this end. Any effort along these lines becomes a noble exercise of charity. For whereas individuals can help others in need, when they join together in initiating social processes of fraternity and justice for all, they enter the ‘field of charity at its most vast, namely, political charity.’ This involves working for a social and political order whose soul is social charity. Once more, I appeal for a renewed appreciation of

politics as “a lofty vocation and one of the highest forms of charity, inasmuch as it seeks the common good” (FT 180).

As for the relationship between the various religions, Francis continues to direct the dialogue not around ideas about God, but rather to the appreciation of every human person as a creature called to be a child of God. This, to begin with, always allows each religion to “contribute significantly to building fraternity and defending justice in society. Dialogue between the followers of different religions does not take place simply for the sake of diplomacy, consideration or tolerance. In the words of the Bishops of India, ‘the goal of dialogue is to establish friendship, peace and harmony, and to share spiritual and moral values and experiences in a spirit of truth and love’” (FT 271).

The eighth chapter – “Religions at the Service of Fraternity in the World” – is particularly clear if we read what Charles de Foucauld said about his hermitage at Béni Abbès, where he welcomed the visits of nomads and people in general: “In the ‘Fraternity’ – as he called his hermitage – to always be humble, sweet and serve, just as Jesus and Mary and Joseph did in the holy house of Nazareth... Sweetness, humility, abjection, charity, serving others” (Fares, 2020).

8. The Call to Live in Hope

“I offer this social encyclical as a modest contribution to continued reflection, in the hope that in the face of present-day attempts to eliminate or ignore others, we may prove capable of responding *with a new dream of fraternity and social friendship* that will not remain at the level of words” (FT 6; italics ours). (Fares, 2020)

A reaction is necessary given the magnitude of the world crisis affecting us on all sides. The pope invites us to react not with words, but with a new dream, that dream realised by Francis of Assisi and Charles de Foucauld with small gestures of a radicality that carries within itself a seed of universal expansion. Francis

proposes the concrete example of the many ordinary people who reacted generously in the face of the unexpected pandemic of Covid-19: “The recent pandemic enabled us to recognise and appreciate once more all those around us who, in the midst of fear, responded by putting their lives on the line” (FT 54, Fares, 2020)

The pages of his encyclical, according to the pope, “do not claim to offer a complete teaching on fraternal love, but rather to consider its universal scope, its openness to every man and woman” (FT 6). This love, capable of extending beyond borders “has as its basis what we call ‘social friendship’ in every city and in every country.” “Genuine social friendship within a society makes true universal openness possible” (FT 99). This is the dynamic contained in the words of St. Francis who declares “blessed is he who loves the other ‘when he is as far from him as if he were next to him’” (FT 1), those who are distant – from a geographical, cultural, ideological, political, or religious point of view – as much as those who are closest. (Fares, 2020) (Fares, 2020)

Fratelli Tutti has the style of a conversation between friends, of those conversations from which, dealing with the vital issues that challenge us and move us, more than mere definitions, inspire our interest in the concrete hope that comes from this friendly and fraternal way of speaking (Fares, 2020). That changes the partners in conversation and their worlds!

Conclusion

The parable of the Good Samaritan, which is the basis of *Fratelli Tutti*, begs every person of good will to examine that key aspect of human life that every Christian knows is true: *in giving we receive*. The pouring forth of selfless love,

the imitation of Christ the Good Shepherd who laid down his life for his sheep, alone offers the restless heart peace. Pope Francis puts it this way: “The parable clearly does not indulge in abstract moralizing, nor is its message merely social and ethical. It speaks to us of an essential and often forgotten aspect of our common humanity: we were created for a fulfilment that can only be found in love” (Briscoe, 2020).

Whether the suffering we encounter is racial injustice, sickness, poverty or exhausted politics, only love born of compassion and sacrifice will bring aid to our afflicted sisters and brothers (Pandikattu 2002).

The parable provides a poignant examination of our interior selves through its characters and their responses to injustice, even evil. There are robbers. Are we robbers? How should robbers be dealt with? Are we merely devout passers-by? Are we the injured man? What inhibits us from being Good Samaritans?

In order to further the goods of fraternity and social friendship, Pope Francis instructs us: “All of us have a responsibility for the wounded.” It is, after all, in the stranger, the prisoner, the hungry and thirsty, and the sick, that we find ourselves meeting Christ (Mt. 25:35-36).

In the classical philosophical and theological tradition, to be a friend to another means to see another’s good as one’s own. St. Thomas Aquinas says of friendship, “a certain mutual love is requisite, since friendship is between friend and friend” (ST II-II, q. 23, a. 1). To be a Good Samaritan, to be willing to regard another as neighbour, seems to require something of the offering of the hand of friendship: to desire for another his or her true good (Briscoe, 2020).

Here we do not need to enumerate the challenges that such a project faces. What we need to embrace is the hope that such an undertaking is possible. And it is.

Far from being a utopian fantasy, sacrificial love is to be had all around us. The Good Shepherd himself pours into our worn and

wear and wary hearts the ever-new wine of charity. This wine will fill us, warm us, and vivify us.

There is always hope to be had in the Gospel. Jesus will extend his invitation to self-renunciation and compassion again, and again, and again. Pope Francis encourages us, saying: “Each day offers us a new opportunity, a new possibility. We should not expect everything from those who govern us, for that would be childish. We have the space we need for co-responsibility in creating and putting into place new processes and changes” (FT 77).

When next we find ourselves on the road, whether today, tomorrow or soon after, let us find ourselves, that is, let us discover again the things truly worth spending our lives for, by loving our neighbour (Briscoe, 2020). Charles de Foucauld will accompany us. Francis Assisi will follow us. On the path of living and sustaining hope! Hope for a just, egalitarian and love-filled world! A world of care, concern and compassion, especially for the weak and vulnerable!

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